

A Frog Paws Log Periodic Antenna with Lateral Circular Patch for UWB Applications

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Abstract - In this paper we propose a new Planar Log-Periodic antenna, called Frog Paw Log-Periodic Dipole Array (FPLPDA). The antenna was based on Carrel's design, inserting lateral circular patches (LCP) into the dipoles to reduce the lower-frequency limit (LFL). The FPLPDA antenna was analyzed with Ansys HFSS software and compared to a Log-Periodic Dipole Array (LPDA) with the Carrel design for 1.5 to 4.0 GHz operation. The FPLPDA operated from 1.1 to 4.5 GHz with reflection coefficient (S11) less than -10 dB, increasing the bandwidth, reducing the LFL.

Index Terms— log-periodic antenna, planar antennas, simulation, UWB, patches.

INTRODUCTION

Log-Periodic antennas are directive antennas, wideband and with stable gain, having their properties varying logarithmically and periodically along their bandwidth [1, 2]. These antennas are widely used in civil, industrial and military applications due to their ease of design, geometry with low complexity, besides being possible to define their desired bandwidth and directivity, being a great option for application in several signal transmission and reception technologies, such as in Ultra-Wideband (UWB) communication systems, Wi-Fi, GPS, Bluetooth, radar systems and electromagnetic compatibility tests (EMC) [3, 4].

Among the Log-Periodic antennas the most used is the Log-Periodic Dipole Array (LPDA) antenna, proposed by DuHamel [2]. The LPDA is formed by dipoles with dimensions that follow a logarithmic relation. Through the techniques and design equations implemented by Carrel and Isbell [5, 6] it is possible to design antennas that operate in large bandwidths.

This work proposes a new antenna planar called Frog Paws Log Periodic Dipole Array (FPLPDA), based on the LPDA antenna with Carrel design, inserting lateral circular patches (LCP) in the dipoles to reduce the lower-frequency limit (LFL). The antenna was compared with the Carrel design at frequencies from 1.0 GHz to 4.5 GHz by computational methods in Ansys HFSS software and the FLPDA was prototyped.

DEVELOPMENT

The FPLPDA antenna was based on the LPDA antenna with Carrel's design techniques and equations, described in [1] and [2]. The antenna uses the concept of independent frequencies, where each dipole with lateral circular patches (DLCP) is responsible for radiating in a frequency range of the antenna's bandwidth.

Carrel's equations used the scaling factor (τ) and the spacing factor (σ). The coefficient σ is used to calculate the initial spacing between the two largest dipoles and therefore directly impacts the size of the

antenna, while the τ defines the antenna's log-periodic relationships, being used to calculate the length (L_n), thickness (W_n) and spacing (S_n) between adjacent dipoles, where "n" ranges from 1 to the number of dipoles on the antenna. In this work, we also applied the coefficient τ for the circular patch radius (R_n). By the design proposed by Carrel, the optimal σ is generally adopted according to the choice of τ , which can be defined from the Carrel graph [2, 5].

The chosen substrate was FR4, with a relative electrical permittivity of 4.5, dielectric loss tangent 0.02 and a thickness of 1.5 mm. To feed the dipoles, microstrip line with a thickness of 3 mm (W_m) with a characteristic impedance of 50 Ω was used. The FLPDA antenna used as a reference for the FPLPDA project was proposed to operate at frequencies from 1.5 to 4GHz.

The thickness of the largest dipole (W_1) and its LCP radius (R_1) were optimized using computational methods. In FPLPDA, an LCP was inserted at the end of each dipole with a radius equal to $R_1 = 2 \times W_1$. The common dipole of LPDA (DC) and the DLCP of FLPDA were designed with dimensions $L_1 = 37$ mm and $W_1 = 3.2$ mm, also, DLCP has $R_1 = 6.4$ mm.

Fig 1 presents the proposed design of the FPLPDA, while Table 1 provides detailed dimensions of the antennas FPLPDA and LPDA.

Figure 1 – Design FPLPDA.

Table 1 – Design Parameters FPLPDA

Dipole	L_n [mm]	W_n [mm]	R_n [mm]
1	37.00	3.20	6.40
2	29.60	2.56	5.12
3	23.68	2.05	4.10
4	18.94	1.64	3.28
5	15.16	1.31	2.62
6	12.12	1.05	2.10
7	9.70	0.84	1.68
8	7.76	0.67	1.34
9	6.21	0.54	1.07

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In Fig. 2, the reflection coefficient (S_{11}) of the FPLPDA and LPDA antenna is presented. The LFL is reduced from 1.32 to 1.10 GHz with addition of LCP on the antenna dipoles.

Figure 2 – S_{11} FPLPDA.

The simulated results when compared with the experimental results of the FPLPDA are very similar. The LFL and maximum frequency limit (MFL) are well defined, as are the resonances and the behaviour of the S_{11} . The FPLPDA antenna operated from 1.10 to 4.50 GHz while the LPDA from 1.35 to 1.75 GHz, 1.86 to 2.40 GHz, and 2.44 to 4.50 GHz with S_{11} less than -10dB. In this way, an FPLPDA increased the bandwidth by 400MHz.

In the Fig. 3 the realized gain (G_R) is simulated from 1 to 4.5GHz with a step of 250MHz. The FPLPDA antenna in relation to the LPDA, decrease in G_R around 2 dBi. The peak G_R of LPDA is 8dBi at 4.25GHz, while FPLPDA has its peaks at 3.25 and 4.25 MHz with 6dBi.

Figure 3 – Realized Gain (dBi)

Fig. 4 shows the radiation pattern at frequencies of 1.1, 2.4 and 4.0GHz. The radiation pattern of the experimental FPLPDA was evaluated at a frequency of 2.4GHz, with a step of 10 degrees, while the simulated results have a step of 2 degrees.

As expected, at 1.1 GHz, the FPLPDA antenna has higher main and back lobes than the PLPDA, and the shape is very close to the radiation pattern of a dipole. At 2.4 GHz, the FPLPDA antenna has smaller back lobes than the LPDA. When comparing experimental and simulated results, the side lobes are larger and

there is an asymmetry in the radiation pattern caused by the position of the coaxial cable. At 4.0 GHz, the FPLPDA has more side lobes than the PLPDA, with a larger beam angle and large back lobe.

Figure 4 – Radiation Pattern

CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we proposed FPLPDA antenna and compared it with the PLPDA based on the Carrel project. The FPLPDA has circular patches at the ends of the lateral dipoles, which made it possible to reduce the LFL and operate at frequencies from 1.1 to 4.5 GHz with S_{11} less than -10dB, improving the bandwidth at 400MHz and the radiation pattern at 2.4GHz, compared to the LPDA. The FPLPDA was therefore efficient and can be used for UWB applications.

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